

ISic1344

Funerary inscription for Agathe

Language

Type

Material

Object

Editor

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Autopsy

2016.10.15

Last Change

2017-07-06 - Jonathan Prag added elements for parallel Italian

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Museo Civico di
Catania, inventory 719

Physical Description

A circular disc of marble, with the reverse cut to form a lid or cover. It is unclear if this is original, or a sign of later reworking. There is some damage / material lost from the lower right edge.

Dimensions

Height 24.5 cm

Width 24.5 cm

Depth 1.5-3.9 cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1-9: 8-21 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation not recorded: mm

Text

1. Ἀγάθη
2. □ ἐτελεύτησεν
3. ἐτῶν ξ παρα □
4. ε σ κευῆ ταῖς τέξ θ ἀπό κα
5. λανδῶν Σεπτεμ
6. βρίων · ἐξεκομίσθη
7. δαὶ Σαββάτοις ·
8. χαρίσου τῷ Κυρίῳ
9. καὶ τῷ Χριστῷ

Apparatus

An eleven-point star is engraved between lines 1 and 2

The first letter on the stone is ε; in place of τῆς one would expect ταῖς
χάρις οὔ Kaibel, Ferrua; χάρις οὔν Agnello

Translation (en)

Agathe completed sixty years on the Day of Preparation, nine days after the
Kalends of September. She
was laid out on the Sabbath. May you be pleasing to God and to
Christ.

Translation (it)

Agathe ha compiuto sessant'anni nel giorno della preparazione, nove giorni
dopo le calende di
settembre. Fu deposta il sabato. Che tu sia gradita a Dio e a Cristo.

Commentary

Although the text is clearly Christian, the names of the days are those of the
Hebrew tradition. Both the vocabulary and the formulae are relatively unusual.
Agathe (and Agathon) was a popular name in both Catania and Siracusa in the
early Christian period, presumably in part at least because of the cult of Saint
Agathe (see ISic0964 inv. no.231). The stone has been cut to form a cover for an
urn; however, while it is possible that the cutting of the reverse is a result of
later re-use, the layout of the text (see above) shows that the face of the stone
was already circular before it was engraved.

Digital identifiers:

TM 492952

PHI 140841

PHI 316255

PHI 333753

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Photo J.Prag